

DEFINING PRIORITIES AND KNOWLEDGE GAPS FOR LUNAR RETURN SAMPLE CHAINS. L. Griffiths¹, T. D. Mikesell¹, F. McDonald², G. Consuma², P. Pirie¹, J. Carpenter², C. Hahn², C. Sætre¹, A. Hutzler^{2,3}, M. Martin⁴, G. Dublet-Aldi¹, V. S. Quinteros¹ and T. Kim¹, ¹Norwegian Geotechnical Institute (NGI), P.O. Box. 3930 Ullevål Stadion, NO-0806 Oslo, Norway, ²European Space Agency, European Space Research and Technology Centre (ESA/ESTEC), Directorate of Human and Robotic Exploration, Keplerlaan 1, 2201 AZ Noordwijk, the Netherlands, ³MEDES for ESA; ⁴European Space Agency (ESA/ECSAT), Fermi Avenue, Harwell Campus, Oxfordshire, OX11 0FD, United Kingdom

Introduction: As lunar exploration increasingly incorporates sample return missions, ensuring the scientific integrity of collected materials is paramount. For example, volatile species can occur as solid ices throughout the solar system [1]. These materials have complex phase equilibria and returning pristine samples to Earth for laboratory analysis remains a significant technical challenge for engineers and scientists. This abstract reports on the progress of an ongoing study conducted by the Norwegian Geotechnical Institute (NGI) under contract to the European Space Agency (ESA).

This study is dedicated to defining European science requirements and addressing critical knowledge gaps in the lunar return sample technology chain so that priorities and needs can be defined and used to support future decisions. By identifying the sample types and sensitive, transient properties of scientific interest, synthesizing expert consensus, and evaluating technical uncertainties, this project aims to establish a roadmap that supports Europe's ability to address key lunar science questions, many of which can only be answered through the return of well-preserved samples.

Survey and Expert Assessment: The first phase of this project involves a comprehensive international survey designed to capture the diverse sample requirements of the lunar scientific community. The survey is structured into several topical areas to ensure that key aspects of the return sample chain, i.e., from the lunar surface to terrestrial scientific laboratory, are addressed. Initial survey sections establish the expert profile, capturing years of experience and specific history with extraterrestrial samples (e.g., Apollo, OSIRIS-REx), which provides a weighted context for the technical requirements that follow.

A primary focus is placed on *Science Requirements* and *Samples*. Respondents are asked to identify the key science questions that require new lunar samples, and to specify the transient properties, such as volatile presence, magnetic signatures, and dust activation, which are most at risk during the return journey. By asking experts to define the specific lithologies and geological events they need to sample, we aim to map scientific intent directly to the sample properties - physical, mechanical, chemical, biological - that must be preserved.

The survey also addresses *Sample Handling Logistics* and *Laboratory Infrastructure* for sample investigation, attempting to determine the minimum

sample mass required for various analytical techniques and the necessity of specialized curation and handling during return and once on Earth. By exploring terrestrial scientific laboratory needs, the survey combines scientific priorities with terrestrial laboratory constraints to establish return chain requirements from the end-user perspective. This allows requirements to be prioritised according to their scientific impact and technical feasibility, while also identifying where investment in hardware capabilities may be needed to fully exploit returned samples.

Preliminary Results and Trends: It should first be noted that the survey is ongoing at the time of writing, and we plan to present results from the completed survey at the ELS 2026 meeting. Early results from the survey indicate a high priority for undisturbed, cryogenically preserved samples, particularly from the lunar polar regions. Some respondents have emphasized that for specific sample types, protection from shocks and thermal spikes is a critical requirement for the validity of the science. For example, some respondents have identified a concern about "physical and textural changes" occurring during the transit from the Moon to Earth, and some respondents have noted that while chemical contamination is a known risk, the mechanical degradation of delicate vesicular "foams" or the loss of stratigraphic orientation during re-entry vibrations represents a major knowledge gap and challenge to answering key scientific questions. Such findings of the survey will directly inform the prioritization matrix in the definition and prioritization step, and we plan to share this information during the ELS presentation.

Science Definition and Prioritization: Building on the survey results, the project will establish a prioritized framework for return sample science. This definition work focuses on characterizing the "Return Sample Chain", attempting to identify every touchpoint where sample disturbance might occur, from the initial collection (e.g., by drilling) and sealing on the lunar surface to reception at curation facilities and subsequent scientific analysis on Earth. We will report here on the initial prioritization of scientific goals (noting the expert survey and follow up interviews are still ongoing at the time of writing), which, for example, may rank the preservation of certain volatile species or the maintenance of stratigraphic integrity as the highest-tier requirements for upcoming missions. This prioritization will serve as a basis to evaluate current technology readiness and identify where existing

hardware may fail to meet the identified (and likely very stringent) scientific standards.

Conclusions: By integrating expert insights to prioritize scientific needs and priorities, this project will create a framework necessary to design the next generation of lunar sample return hardware. The goal is to ensure that when new lunar samples arrive on Earth, they provide a faithful record of the lunar environment that enables high-quality and high-impact scientific discovery about lunar and solar system evolution.

References:

[1] Gilbertson D. L. et al. (2026) GRL, 53, *e2025GL117103*.